

University of
Nottingham
UK | CHINA | MALAYSIA

UNIVERSITY OF
DELAWARE

TURNEYES 892951

RESEARCHER ANNEMARIE WALTER
OUTGOING SUPERVISOR DAVID REDLAWSK
INCOMING SUPERVISOR CEES VAN DER EIJK

REPORT 5

PRESENTATION ANNUAL
MEETING OF THE
INTERNATIONAL
SOCIETY OF POLITICAL
PSYCHOLOGY, JULY 13-16,
2022, ATHENS, GREECE

November 2024

The project Turning a Blind Eye to Scandal has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 892951

The University of
Nottingham

**Partisan Differences in Punitiveness in
Response to Politicians' Moral Transgressions**

David Redlawsk and Annemarie Walter

1

Research Question

- Do US partisan voters differ in punitiveness in response to politicians' moral violations and whether these differences persist when controlling for voters' perceptions of severity of moral violations.

2

Hypotheses

3

- **Partisanship Hypothesis (H1):** Republicans have a stronger desire to punish politicians' involved in moral transgressions than Democrats
- **In party Bias Hypothesis (H2):** Voters have a stronger desire to punish outgroup politicians involved in moral transgressions than ingroup politicians involved in moral transgressions
- **Perceived Severity Hypothesis (H3):** The more morally wrong voters perceive the politician's moral transgression the stronger their desire for punishment of the transgressing politician.

3

Experimental Design

4

- A vignette study using a between-subjects experiment in a 6 x 3 design embedded in a survey questionnaire administered to approximately 3000 U.S. voters
- We manipulated the moral principle violated (Care, Fairness, Loyalty, Authority and Sanctity) and added a social norm violation as a baseline
- We manipulated the partisanship of the politician (Republican, Democrat, no partisanship) in the vignette
- Each respondent was randomly assigned a short vignette describing a fictional, but realistic sounding, scenario
- Data were collected between 2 October 2020 and 3 November 2020 by Dynata
- We restrict analyses to 2074 partisan voters exposed to a moral violation

4

Stimulus Material

5

Norm violated	Vignette (non-partisan)
Care	You see a politician make fun of a constituent with mental health problems.
Fairness	You see a politician making sure that those who voted for him get first access to jobs.
Loyalty	You see a politician in your town say the neighboring town is better.
Authority	You see a politician violating safety regulations ordered by the Chief of Police at a disaster.
Sanctity	You see a politician was found having sex with a teenager.
Social	You see a politician carrying briefing papers to the capitol in a plastic grocery bag

5

Punitiveness Scale

6

Individual Items							
	Labels	RC	Mean	Standard Deviation	H _i	Z	DM
1	The politician should apologize to the public for his/her behavior	N	3.7106	1.4331	.7614	80.9204	Y
2	The politician should apologize to all parties involved for his/her behavior	N	3.6831	1.4405	.7580	80.8318	Y
3	The politician should restore the damage done by his/her behavior	N	3.5816	1.3932	.7177	76.5392	Y
4	The politician should be removed from office because of his/her behavior	N	3.0966	1.5555	.6864	72.4233	Y
5	The politician should receive a warning for his/her behavior from the party leader	N	3.3820	1.4859	.6504	69.2458	Y
6	This politician should because of his/her behavior be reported to authorities	N	3.2162	1.5625	.7010	74.6550	Y
Scale							
	Punitiveness, i.e. the desire to punish		Mean	Standard Deviation	H	Z	
			20.6702	7.6023	.7118	131.0212	

6

7

8

The Effect of Partisanship on Voters' Punitiveness

9

9

The Effect of Partisanship on Voters' Punitiveness of Politicians' Moral Transgressions at Different Levels of Perceived Severity

10

10

In-party Bias of Democrats and Republicans' Punitiveness of Politicians' Moral Transgressions at Different Levels of Severity

11

11

Conclusions

12

- When voters perceive the severity of the moral violation committed to be low, Republicans have a stronger desire to punish than Democrats. When voters perceive the severity of the moral transgression committed to be moderate or high in severity, Democrats have a stronger desire to punish the politician involved than Republicans.
- Republicans' levels of punitiveness depend on the group of the transgressor, i.e. higher levels of punitiveness for the out party than in party transgressors. Regardless, the level of perceived severity of the moral transgression, Democrats do not show an in-party bias in their desire to punish.
- Not only do the results show partisan voters' heterogeneity in punitiveness, but also that this relationship is strongly mediated by perceived severity.

12

- This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 892951